

EFFECT OF ADDING MAGNESIUM OXIDE NANOPARTICLES ON HYDROXYL METHYL CELLULOSE BASED FILMS: PHYSICO-CHEMICAL, MECHANICAL AND RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

NOUR-DJIHANE MAZOUZI ^{1*}, KHALIDA BOUTEMAK ¹, AHMAD HADDAD ²

¹ Laboratoire d'Analyse Fonctionnelle Des Procédés Chimiques, Département Du Génie Des Procédés, Faculté De Technologie, Université Blida 1, Blida, Algérie

² Laboratoire De Corrosion, Centre De Recherche En Technologie Industrielle, Alger, Algérie

Films based on hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC) find applications in for various applications due to their environmental nature, low cost, flexibility and transparency. However, the mechanical properties and moisture content need to be improved. The point of this study was to examine the impact of the magnesium oxide (MgO) addition on the physicochemical, mechanical and rheological properties of hydroxymethylcellulose films. HPMC/MgO composite films showed a four-fold increase in mechanical properties compared to unreinforced HPMC films. In addition, the addition of MgO nanoparticles reduced the moisture content to 2%. The latter was influenced by the difference in water solubility of various composite films, the incorporation of MgO into HPMC films improved the water barrier properties despite the increased water resistance value. Steam wettability was obtained for the HPMC/MgO composite film.

Keywords: hydroxypropyl methylcellulose HPMC, magnesium oxide MgO, nanoparticles, rheological properties

1. Introduction

Polymeric nanocomposites are considered as an important technological topic in many engineering applications [1]. Natural polymers such as polysaccharides, proteins, and lipid-based films offer a variety of valuable properties, including environmental friendliness, food packaging, biodegradability, biocompatibility and durability [2].

The use of natural biopolymers in synthetic materials has been tested recently. At the laboratory scale, many researches have been investigate the ability of natural polymers as in: starch, chitosan, pectin, gluten, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) to synthesize food packaging/biodegradable films, but their mechanical properties and barrier properties prevent them for being used as alternatives to synthetic materials. HPMC is a cellulose derivative that is widely used as a biopolymer matrix for controlled delivery systems due to its accessibility, biocompatibility, water solubility and nontoxicity [3]. However, films based on natural biopolymers such as HPMC is also limited with their low mechanical strength, poor barrier properties and the extremely sensitive to environmental conditions.

Researchers have studied and developed polymer composite systems. They thought that adding inorganic components to polymers would improve their properties. Nanoparticles have been found to affect the properties of the base polymer [4]. Nanocomposite films are defined as bio-based polymers with nanometre-sized fillers. The biopolymer acts as a matrix for the nanocomposite film and is reinforced with interspersed nanofiller to improve the properties of the polymer and increase

its performance characteristics [5]. It can also be used as an active item [6]. Materials based on nanoscale metal oxides provide a solution to meet current and future technological needs due to their innovative properties [7]. Magnesium oxide (MgO) is viewed as a valuable material in both basic and applied research [8]. Furthermore, due to its simple stoichiometry, high ionic properties, and crystalline structure, it is considered a unique material that can be formed into a variety of particle shapes and sizes [9]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no research on the influence of MgO NP/HPMC film properties has been achieved.

The aim of our study was to investigate the Mechanical properties, water vapor permeability, mechanical properties and rheological properties of films of HPMC films with the addition of MgO NPs.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (hydroxypropyl content of ~10%, methyl content of ~29%, degree of substitution of 1.4, average degree of polymerization of 750) was purchased from Shandong Heda Co., Ltd. Glycerol obtained from Yongda Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd (Tianjin, China), magnesium nanoxyde (MgO) powder (a particle size of 50 ~ 100 nm, >99%) obtained from L'Urederra technological centre (Spain).

2.2. Composite film elaboration

Films were prepared by the solution method as described by (Jean-Marie Raquez & al. 2013) [10] with slight modification; The HPMC dissolved in water was weighed and stirred by using a magnetic

*Autor corespondent/Corresponding author,
E-mail: mazouzi.nourdjihane@gmail.com

Table 1

Different polymers and NPs used in the formulation of bio composites FFS.							
Samples	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
HPMC%	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
MgO%	0	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1	5

stirrer at 20 ° C for 24 hours to prepare HPMC solution (3 wt. %), the HPMC solution was mixed with Glycerol (20 wt % of dry matter) as a plasticizers agent, and stirred gently until it become a clear solution. Then the final mixture was reinforced by adding Magnesium oxide dissolved in distillate water, with different concentration varied from 0%, 0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5%, 0.7%, 1%, 5% of dry matter, in order to prepare HPMC-MgO bio-nanocomposite films (**Table 1**), finally, the film forming solution was poured into a Petri dish (d = 60 mm) and dried at 20 ± 2 °C for 24 h.

3.Characterizations

3.1. Physicochemical properties of films
Measurement of film thickness

The thickness of the prepared film was measured at three different locations using a digital Vernier Calliper micrometer (Aerospace LCD digital Vernier Caliper-150 MM), and the characteristics of the film were measured using the average thickness.

Biodegradation test

The biodegradability of the samples was evaluated by measuring the mass loss of the compounds as a function of time in the composting environment. The samples are weighed and placed in a compost bin at a depth of 12-15 cm. It was left for 10 days. The mass loss assessment was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\text{Mass loss}\% = \frac{m_i - m_f}{m_i} \times 100 \quad \text{eq.1}$$

With:

Mf: The final mass of the tested sample.

Mi: The initial mass of the tested sample [11].

Humidity level

After preparing the various formulations, the samples are weighed and recorded (m0) before entering the oven. Drying continues and the dough is considered complete (about 48 hours).

Moisture levels were determined according to standard (NF M 03-002)

$$.H\% = \frac{m_0 - m}{m_0} \times 100 \quad \text{eq.2}$$

3.2. Mechanical properties

The traction test involves subjecting a standardized test tube to a single-axial effort until the rupture to determine the mechanical characteristics of the material such as elasticity limit, break resistance and breakage lengthening [12].

The tests are carried out at room temperature on standardized test tubes (films) and sized from 30-50-0.05 mm. In addition, the mechanical properties of different films were evaluated using a traction machine (capacity mark of 600 kN, The pre-conditioned samples were subjected to a constant speed of 1 mm/min until breaking, and from the automatically recorded stress/deformation curves (Force (F) in N depending on the length (ΔL) in millimetres), which is calculated by the maximum stress at the break δ (MPa):

$$\delta = \frac{F_{\max}}{s} \quad \text{eq.3}$$

With:

S: is the initial section of the test tube (m2) and equals the product of thickness by its width;

F_{max}: maximum force at break (N).

The Young E elasticity module or module (MPa) corresponds to the gradient of the linear part of the curve (deformation constraint) to the small deformations.

$$E = \frac{\delta}{\epsilon} \quad \text{eq.4}$$

With: δ: stress (N/m² or MPa) and ε, deformation (%).

The percentage of nominal deformation (lengthening) of the film at the breaking point % It corresponds to the ratio between lengthening and reference length (initial).

$$\epsilon = \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} \times 100 \quad \text{eq.5}$$

With:

ΔL= l - l₀: Lengthening at the break (mm).

l₀: initial length of test tube

L: final length of test tube [13].

3.3. Water vapor permeability

Water vapor permeability is defined as the amount of water that passes through a unit area of the film in a unit of time. Samples from dry film sheets are cut in a circular manner. The sample is prepared by filling the cavity of glass bottles with distilled water, covering them with round plastic and silicon ring, then tightly closing the bottle with an aluminium cap. The bottle is weighed and then placed in a desiccator, which creates an atmosphere of 58% relative humidity or low relative humidity (around 0%). They are kept at a specific temperature for 72 hours and weighed at predetermined intervals. Based on the weight loss W (g) of the bottles, the water vapor permeability is calculated as the amount of water permeating

through the membrane with respect to the area $A(\text{cm}^2)$ and time t (h) [14]

$$\text{WVP} = w. A. t \quad \text{eq.6}$$

3.4. FTIR-ATR

FTIR-ATR spectra were recorded on Agilent Cary 630 FTIR Spectrometer. From 4000-650 cm^{-1} wavelength range, via directly using the solid film sample and data acquisition with IR-solution software. The spectra obtained were used to determine the film matrix's interactions.

3.5. Scanning electron microscopy analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses were performed using a Philips CM120 Bio-filter with an SEM module at an accelerating voltage of 120 kV. Crude MgO nanoparticles were analysed by placing a drop of nanoparticle suspension (0.1% (w/w)) in distilled water on an aluminium-coated grid. The dispersion of MgO in the HPMC matrix was evaluated using ultrathin sections of the nanocomposites [15].

3.6. Rheological behaviour

Controlled stress rheometer (MCR 302, Anton Paar Physical, GmbH, Germany) was used for all rheological analysis with parallel plate geometry (gap 0.5 mm and diameter 25 mm) and RheoPlus US200 software (Anton Paar, GmbH, Germany) was used to process the test results. The film-forming solution was analysed at 20 °C with a controlled shear rate.

Experimental flow curves expressing the variation of apparent viscosity with shear rate ($\eta_{\text{app}} = f(\dot{\gamma})$) were determined and fitted with the Carreau structural model, which is used to characterize the flow behavior of polymer dispersions and other shear-thinning fluids [16].

$$\frac{\eta - \eta_{\infty}}{\eta_0 - \eta_{\infty}} = \frac{1}{(1 - k\dot{\gamma})^{2P}} \quad \text{eq.7}$$

The parameter η_0 represents zero viscosity; it expresses the viscous behavior of the suspension at zero shear rates. In contrast, η_{∞} is the infinite shear viscosity, which expresses the behavior of a suspension with extreme shear. K is the time constant and P is the exponent to determine the viscoelastic properties. The gels were analysed at 20 °C in oscillatory shear mode at a frequency of 1 Hz. Two viscoelastic parameters (storage modulus, G' and loss modulus, G'') were evaluated. Their values were derived in the linear viscoelastic region (LVE region) and labelled G'_{LVE} and G''_{LVE} , respectively [17].

Measurements were performed in duplicate and experimental data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The statistical analysis was performed non-linear rheological models using the statistical software.8, comparing 95% confidence intervals ($p < 0.05$).

Fig.1 - Film appearance after drying.

4. Results and discussion

The different bio composites MgO NPs/HPMC films obtained have a homogeneous, thin, transparent, flexible appearance Fig.1.

4.1. Physicochemical properties of films

The film thickness varies by changing the compositions of the FFS, another factor impact the thickness of films is viscosity, thus the HPMC films forming system is based on HPMC gel that is why films are thicker than the reinforced ones, the biodegradability test shows that bio composites films has been destroyed around twice as much as that HPMC one (0.1% MgO NPs/HPMC and 0.5% MgO NPs/HPMC), the incorporation of MgO NPs (0.5%) significantly improved the biodegradation properties of the film which made of it a better choice for environment, in the other side the table 2 shows also that the humidity level increasing by adding MgO NPs to the HPMC matrix till 0.7% of MgO NPs over that it decrease, these results significate that there is an impact of MgO NPs on HPMC films.

Table2

Physicochemical properties of films.			
Samples	Thickness (mm)	Mass loss%	H%
F0	0.04 ±0.01	13.33	12.93
F1	0.03±0.01	21.08	14.44
F2	0.03±0.01	16.67	13.15
F3	0.03±0.01	26.5	14.52
F4	0.03±0.01	20	16.43
F5	0.02±0.01	12.5	12.36
F6	0.03±0.01	8.33	12.77

4.2. Mechanical and water vapour permeability properties

Mechanical properties of the biocomposites films were reported in table 3. It has been reported that the addition of the MgO NPs has an effect on HPMC matrix as shown by the tensile strength (δR) and the elongation at break values ($\epsilon R\%$); $\epsilon R\%$ significantly increased till 31.46 % as showing on film. Based on HPMC/0.7% MgO NPs, and both of the δR , the WVP decreased comparing with HPMC

Table 3

Mechanical properties and water vapor permeability (WVP) of HPMC film.

Samples	$\epsilon_R\%$	$\delta_R(\text{MPa})$	E(MPa)	WVP (g.mm/kPa.m ² .h)
F0	16.95	25.79	2,79	0,329
F1	15.11	32.9	18,14	0,315
F2	24.22	18.4	10,25	0,321
F3	19.72	12.53	29,93	0,319
F4	31.46	12.96	16,78	0,317
F5	13.29	18.65	40,98	0,326
F6	30.75	13.89	17,79	0,334

Fig.2 - FTIR spectroscopy of bio composites films.

film. The Addition of MgO NPs had slightly a significant effect on flexibility of HPMC film.

4.3.FTIR-ATR

The spectrum in Fig.2 represents the infrared spectrum of the films; the spectra of the FT-IR analysis represent the characteristic bands of Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) reinforced with MgO NPs. The plateau formed between the 3040 cm⁻¹ and 3600 cm⁻¹ vibration is due to the fusion of the two peaks of the alcohol (-OH) and aliphatic alkane (-CH₂, CH₃) groups; however, By comparing the characteristic bands of the infrared spectra of the HPMC, it can be estimated that there is no chemical interaction present because there are no appearances or disappearances of new spectral bands.

4.4.Morphological analysis

The surface morphology of the film is shown in Fig. 3. SEM images indicate that all film samples are small and uniform. The incorporation of MgO NPs into the FFS occupied the free volume and inhibited the microstructure of the HPMC films, thereby improving the barrier properties of the HPMC films [3]. A uniform distribution of MgO NPs was observed in HPMC films made from FFS containing MgO NPs at a concentration of 0.5%, but some aggregation of NPs was observed in films containing MgO NPs above 0.5%. Agglomeration of

NPs at higher concentration was also observed by Ma et al. (2009) and Malik et al. (2022) for pea starch-ZnO bionanocomposite film. Generally the biopolymer is typically effective in preventing the electrostatic interaction of FFS nanoparticles by means of steric stabilization, but when the nanostructure increases in density, the latter tends to dominate the interplay between nanopores and cause NP clustering.

4.5.Rheological study

In Figure 4.a, the progress of the viscoelastic properties, specifically the conservation modulus G' and loss modulus G'', is depicted as a function of strain. This graph reveals two distinct areas: the first one represents the domain of linear viscoelasticity, known as the Linear Visco-Elastic Range (LVE range), where both moduli remain constant at low strains, with G' being greater than G''.

The film's behavior in this area is solid viscoelastic and deformations are recoverable. This domain is limited by the gel point, where the two modulus cross each other. After this point, we have the second area, where both modulus fall progressively and G'' is greater than G', indicating the liquid behavior of the HPMC films at high deformation ($\gamma < 1\%$) and deformations are not recoverable. The reinforcing films with MgO NPs demonstrate a change in the rheological behavior

Fig. 3 - SEM micrographs of cross-section of the films (a) HPMC (b) HPMC/0.1% MgO(c) HPMC/0.3% MgO (d) HPMC/0.5% MgO (e) HPMC/0.7% MgO (f) HPMC/1% MgO (g) HPMC/5% MgO, with a magnification of 15K x.

Fig.4 - The evolution of the modulus of conservation G' and modulus of loss G'' as a function of the strain

Fig. 5 - Flow curve of the HPMC and biocomposites FFS.

Table 4

The viscosity behavior of ffs at 20 °c of Carreau parameters

samples	Characteristic of viscosity behavior for FFS at 20 °c of Carreau parameters				
	η_0 [Pa.s]	η_∞ [Pa.s]	K [s]	P	R%
F0	12.21	0.33	9.56	1.06	97
F1	9.57	0.018	3.31	0.27	95
F2	8.09	0.017	10.21	0.75	96
F3	7.58	0.023	5.35	0.70	99
F4	7.46	0.010	8.46	0.96	98
F5	8.24	0.008	4.96	0.55	95

Fig.6 - Typical flow curve of the biocomposites FFS fitted by the model of Carreau at 20°C using statistica.

(Fig.4.b). In comparison to HPMC, it is obvious that at low deformations, the storage modulus is constant, which corresponds to the domain of linear viscoelasticity, the LVE range. In this domain, the behavior of the biocomposites films is expected viscoelastic, but the affection of the MgO NPs on the HPMC matrix is shown in the recorded deformations, which indicated that all the biocomposites films (HPMC/MgO NPs) presented typical liquid or viscous behavior with a larger loss modulus (G'') value than storage modulus (G') all samples (Fig.4.c). These deformations are also reversible. G.K. Malik et al (2022) reported similar findings for Nano ZnO - Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC) based suspensions, as did

Chen et al. (2009) for lower concentration starch-based film forming solutions [17]. The collagen HPMC blends with higher HPMC content tend to have a liquid-like behavior as shown by Ding et al. (2015) [2,19].

For the Flow curves Fig.5, rheological behavior is largely described by the viscosity of a fluid which typically depends on the concentration of the solution and the nature of the substance that forms it [19].

Our observations reveal an HPMC sample with a viscosity of 10-100 Pa.s, which is clearly higher than that of HPMC/MgO NP (1-10 Pa.s). As the shear progresses, the viscosity begins to decrease gradually until it reaches a viscosity of

0.01 Pa, which justifies the shear-thinning rheological behavior. Using statistic 8, Figure 6 demonstrated the same rheological behavior in a typical FFS flow curve of Carreau-fit biocomposites at 20 °C..

The fitting results by the Carreau model were satisfactory with R^2 close to 1. This same type of behavior, adjusted by the Cross model, was found varying from 35% to 84%. The values of the four characteristic parameters, η_0 , η_∞ , K and p are presented in Table 4.

5. Conclusion

This paper states that the mechanical and barrier characteristics of the HPMC membrane were improved by the addition of MgO NPs. The SEM image indicates that the free volume of the HPMC matrix was occupied by the MgO NPs through the film, forming microchannel. The viscosity of ffs affected the flexibility and thickness of the film, and the bioassay increased the bioavailability of HPMC films, thus increasing the effect of MgO NPs on HPMC. The rheological behavior of the film-forming system and the structural properties of the HPMC films were influenced by the concentration of NPs. However, the rheological behaviours of all FFS presented a non-Newtonian behavior and was not affected by the concentration of MgO NPs. Viscoelasticity tests showed that all samples were pure HPMC-based films exhibiting elastic solid behavior and o elastic liquid behavior. This makes the film biocomposites useful for coating applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] Magdalena Wrona, Marlene J. Cran, Cristina Nerín, Stephen W. Bigger (2017), Development and characterisation of HPMC films containing PLA nanoparticles loaded with green tea extract for food packaging applications, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.08.094>.
- [2] Annu, Akbar Ali, Shakeel Ahmed (2021), Eco-friendly natural extract loaded antioxidative chitosan/polyvinyl alcohol based active films for food packaging, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06550>.
- [3] Gulshan Kumar Malik, Jayeeta Mitra, Manish Kaushal (2022), Rheology of nano ZnO - Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC) based suspensions and structural properties of resulting films, *Journal of Food Engineering*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2022.111187>.
- [4] Deepalekshmi Ponnamma, John-John Cabibihan, Mariappan Rajan, S. Sundar Pethaiah, Kalim Deshmukh, Jyoti Prasad Gogoi, S.K. Khadheer Pasha, M. Basheer Ahamed, Jagadish Krishnegowda, B.N. Chandrashekar, Anji Reddy Polu, Chun Cheng (2019), Synthesis, optimization and applications of ZnO/polymer nanocomposites, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2019.01.081>.
- [5] Jeffrey George, Hatsuo Ishida (2019), A review on the very high nanofiller-content nanocomposites: Their preparation methods and properties with high aspect ratio fillers, *progress in Polymer Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2018.07.006>.
- [6] Rungsinee Sothornvit (2019), Nanostructured materials for food packaging systems: new functional properties, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2019.03.001>.
- [7] Ramesan, M. T. (2013). Synthesis and Characterization of Magnetolectric Nanomaterial Composed of Fe₃O₄ and Polyindole. *Adv. Polym. Technol.*, 32, 21362. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.21362>.
- [8] Sumithraj PP (2020), Structural and Electrical Studies on Zinc Added Magnesium Oxide Nanoparticle. *J Phys Sci*; 31(3):73-86. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21315/jps2020.31.3.6>.
- [9] A. Sharma, S. Arya, B. Singh, T.A. Prerna, S. Singh, R. Sharma (2020), Sol-gel synthesis of Zn doped MgO nanoparticles and their application, *Integr. Ferroelectr.* 205 14–25, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10584587.2019.1674993>.
- [10] Jean-Marie Raquez, Youssef Habibi, Marius Murariu, Philippe Dubois (2013), Poly(lactide) (PLA)-based nanocomposites, *Progress in Polymer Science*, Volume 38, Issues 10–11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2013.05.014>.
- [11] Chin-San Wu (2011), Preparation, Characterization, and Biodegradability of Renewable Resource Based Composites from Recycled Poly(lactide) Bioplastic and Sisal Fibers, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.34223>.
- [12] Sandeep Karki, Hyeongmin Kim, Seon-Jeong Na, Dohyun Shin, Kanghee Jo, Jaehwi Lee (2016), Thin films as an emerging platform for drug delivery, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajps.2016.05.004>.
- [13] Zurdo Schroeder I, Franke P, Schaefer UF, Lehr CM (2007). Development and characterization of film forming polymeric solutions for skin drug delivery. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* Jan;65(1):111-21. <http://doi:10.1016/j.ejpb.2006.07.015>.
- [14] Kashmiri Kathe and Harsha Kathpalia (2021), Film forming systems for topical and transdermal drug delivery., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajps.2017.07.004>.
- [15] Rao MA (2007). *Rheology of fluid and semisolid foods: principles and applications*. Boston (MA): Springer; <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-9230-6>.
- [16] Erlantz Lizundia, Marie Cristina Penayo, Alain Guinault, Jose Luis Vilas, Sandra Domenech (2019), Impact of ZnO nanoparticle morphology on relaxation and transport properties of PLA nanocomposites, *Polymer Testing*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2019.02.009>.
- [17] Linda Belhadji, Abdelkader HadjSadok & Nadji Moulai-Mostefa (2018) Design and characterization of calcium-free in-situ gel formulation based on sodium alginate and chitosan, *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*, 44:4, 662-669, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03639045.2017.1408640>.
- [18] Chen, C.H., Kuo, W.S., Lai, L.S (2009). Rheological and physical characterization of film-forming solutions and edible films from tapioca starch/decolorized hsian-tsao leaf gum. *Food Hydrocolloids* 23 (8), 2132–2140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.>
- [19] Ding, C., Zhang, M., Li, G., (2015). Preparation and characterization of collagen/ hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) blend film. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 119, 194–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.11.057>.
- [20] Hamiouda Sara, Madiha M. Yahoum, Sonia Lefnaoui, Hadjsadok Abdelkader, Nadji Moulai-Mostefa, (2020), New alkylated xanthan gum as amphiphilic derivatives: Synthesis, physicochemical and rheological studies, *Journal of Molecular Structure*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2020.127768>.
